

The geography of sexual, physical, and emotional violence against children and young people in Namibia

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Summary

This study examined the geospatial patterns and risk factors of violence against children and young people in Namibia using data from the 2019 Violence Against Children and Youth Survey. Our study revealed significant regional disparities in the prevalence of sexual, physical, and emotional violence, with high rates in the central and northern regions. Several risk factors, including *having a romantic partner*, *witnessing domestic violence*, and *living in a single-parent household*, influence violence prevalence. These findings emphasise the need for targeted region-specific interventions and policies to address the identified risk factors and reduce violence against children and young people (VACYP) in Namibia.

Keywords: Violence against children, young people, Namibia, geospatial patterns, area-level data

1. Introduction

Violence against children (VAC) remains a critical public health issue, affecting nearly one billion children under 18 annually through sexual (SV), physical (PV), and emotional violence (EV) (Hillis et al, 2016). Despite global efforts, VAC remains pervasive, often due to cultural norms and beliefs that support physical or psychological punishment in child-rearing (Akmatov, 2011). VAC has long-term developmental consequences for victims that can extend into adulthood if not addressed (Hillis et al, 2017).

Geographical variations in VAC prevalence are well documented, with higher rates in low- and middle-income countries (LIMCs) than in high-income countries. Recent research has focused on understanding the geospatial patterns of VAC, primarily in the Americas, Spain, France, and the UK, although much of this work relies on administrative data from official reports, which often underestimate the true prevalence of VAC compared to self-reported survey data (Shinyemba et al, 2024). Despite the growing recognition of the importance of geographic variation, there is limited research on LIMCs, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where VAC remains widespread and poorly understood.

Understanding the geographical variability of VAC is essential for identifying high-risk areas and guiding the development of targeted interventions and resource allocation. In Namibia, VAC is driven by patriarchal norms and cultural beliefs that normalise violence and the presence of related social problems, such as poverty, crime, alcoholism, and unemployment. Police data indicate that children account for 10% of murder victims and 32% of rape cases, whereas the 2019 Violence Against Children and Youth Survey (VACS) found that 40% of girls and 45% of boys experienced SV, PV, or EV before

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the age of 18 (MGEPESW et al, 2020). Despite evidence of geographical disparities in VAC in Namibia, no study has formally examined its spatial distribution or determinants.

This study aimed to explore the geographic distributions of SV, PV, and EV against children and young people in Namibia. Specifically, it seeks to 1) map the spatial patterns of the area-level prevalence of SV, PV, and EV; 2) assess spatial clustering; 3) identify area-level risk factors driving the prevalence; and 4) analyse how the influence of these risk factors varies across the country.

2. Methods

2.1. Data and sample

Our study followed a cross-sectional ecological design using secondary data from the 2019 Namibia VACS. The VACS is a nationally representative household survey covering non-institutionalised children and youths aged 13-24 years across Namibia's 14 regions. It provides data on experiences of SV, PV, and EV before the age of 18 years, lifetime childhood violence among adolescents aged 13-17, and past year violence. VACS used three-stage cluster sampling, selecting 274 of 3,472 enumeration areas (EAs) and 6,042 households, with 4,211 females and 980 males surveyed.

2.2. Geoprocessing

Data cleaning and coding were performed using IBM SPSS and exported to R for geo-referencing. VACS covered 67% of constituencies and 4% of enumeration areas (EA). Due to limited EA coverage and missing geo-points in the VACS, responses were aggregated at the constituency level to minimise data loss and reduce issues related to the modifiable areal unit problem at the regional level. To enhance reliability, constituencies with fewer than ten respondents were excluded from the analysis, reducing the dataset to 79 areas. This study presents weighted area-level data from 4,199 females and 980 males.

Table 1 Summary statistics of the study variables.

	Mean	Std. dev.	CV
Forms of violence, constituency level prevalence			
Past year SV (%)	7.58	6.68	0.88
Past year PV (%)	21.47	10.44	0.49
Past year EV (%)	25.21	13.23	0.52
Constituency-level explanatory variables			
Currently schooling (%)	61.66	20.54	0.33
Paid/self-employment (%)	24.51	16.24	0.66
Mother alive (%)	87.72	7.11	0.08
No supervision night (%)	40.56	14.22	0.35
Romantic partner (%)	50.6	12.85	0.25
Women beating (%)	14.13	11.76	0.83
Tolerate violence (%)	14.57	10.7	0.73
Fear of violence (%)	7.9	6.76	0.86
Domestic violence (%)	15.75	9	0.57
Abuse of siblings (%)	25.42	12.9	0.51
Community violence (%)	44.87	19.15	0.43
Transactional Relationship (%)	0.59	1.23	2.08
HHs single (%)	42.75	16.69	0.39
HHs no education (%)	12.1	10.53	0.87
HHs government aid (%)	42.91	22.39	0.52

Note : CV – coefficient of variation.

In this study, past-year SV, PV, and EV were calculated as the percentages of respondents in each area who reported violence. SV included unwanted sexual touching, attempted or forced sex, and coerced

sex. PV covered slapping, strangling, and threats with weapons. EV involved belittling by parents, humiliation by intimate partners, and name-calling or exclusion by peers, all experienced in the past 12 months.

We examined area-level risk factors as aggregated percentages, guided by a literature review and socio-ecological framework, which highlights individual-, household-, and community-level influences on violence risk.

We used choropleth maps to visualise the spatial patterns of violence. Pearson's correlation assessed relationships between forms of violence. Global Moran's I measured global spatial autocorrelation, and Local Indicators of Spatial Autocorrelation (*LISA*) identified local hotspots and cold spots. We applied Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression with stepwise selection for risk factor identification. We then used Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to capture local variations. Analyses were conducted using R and GeoDa software.

3. Results and Discussion

The mean prevalence rates of SV, PV, and EV were 7.58%, 21.47%, and 25.21%, respectively (Table 1). We found significant variability in the prevalence of each form of violence and the explanatory variables, with notable variation in mean scores across study areas.

Our results indicated significant spatial variability in the prevalence of SV, PV, and EV throughout Namibia, with the central, northern, and northeastern regions exhibiting the highest rates (Figures 1A–C). These regions are characterised by high population density, poverty, and other social problems. Pearson's correlation analysis showed moderate positive correlations between SV, PV, and EV ($r = 0.413, 0.471, \text{ and } 0.522$, respectively; $p < 0.01$), implying that constituencies with an elevated prevalence of one form of violence often overlap with those of other forms of violence.

Figure 1 Prevalence and LISA clusters of SV, PV, and EV.

Moran's I results revealed significant global spatial autocorrelation for SV ($I = 0.205, p = 0.003$) and EV ($I = 0.180, p = 0.006$). However, PV exhibited weak global spatial autocorrelation ($I = 0.101, p = 0.067$), indicating no significant global clustering. *LISA* showed that SV had more high-prevalence clusters than PV and EV (Figures 1D–F). Hotspots were detected in the northern regions for all forms of violence, in central Namibia for SV and PV, and in the west for PV and EV. In addition, some hotspots of PV and EV overlapped, suggesting similar patterns of spread.

Table 2 OLS regression coefficients.

	SV			PV			EV		
	Coef.	SE	VIF	Coef.	SE	VIF	Coef.	SE	VIF
Intercept	-7.49**	2.46	-	0.23	10.3	-	-5	4.94	-
Paid/self-employment (%)	-0.13***	0.04	1.15						
Romantic partner (%)	0.13*	0.05	1.33						
Domestic violence (%)	0.29***	0.07	1.25						
Abuse of siblings (%)	0.11*	0.05	1.43	0.39***	0.08	1.71	0.29**	0.09	1.52
HHs single (%)	0.10**	0.04	1.25						
Currently schooling (%)				0.13**	0.05	1.43	0.23***	0.05	1.06
Mother alive (%)				-0.18	0.12	1.11			
Tolerate violence (%)				0.19*	0.09	1.48	0.21*	0.09	1.09
Women beating (%)				-0.21*	0.09	1.8			
Community violence (%)				0.23***	0.05	1.59	0.23***	0.06	1.58
HHs government aid (%)				0.18***	0.05	1.96			
HHs no education (%)				0.17.	0.09	1.47			
Transactional Relationship (%)							2.09**	0.78	1.07
No supervision night (%)							-0.23**	0.07	1.1
Fear of violence (%)							0.42**	0.15	1.18
<i>R</i>²		0.494			0.581			0.649	
<i>Adjusted-R</i>²		0.459			0.533			0.615	
<i>AIC_c</i>		485.838			554.837			569.061	

Note : AIC – Akaike information criterion; AIC_c – corrected Akaike information criterion; VIF – variance inflation factor; SE – standard error; and Coef. – coefficient; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, . $p < 0.1$

Table 3 GWR coefficients.

	SV			PV			EV		
	Min.	Mean	Max.	Min.	Mean	Max.	Min.	Mean	Max.
Intercept	-15.6	-8.38	-5.71	-15.96	-3.56	16.04	-11.13	-1.91	10.89
Paid/self-employment (%)	-0.15	-0.11	-0.06						
Romantic partner (%)	0.09	0.15	0.21						
Domestic violence (%)	0.12	0.26	0.49						
Abuse of siblings (%)	0.1	0.13	0.24	0.34	0.38	0.52	0.19	0.33	0.4
HHs single (%)	0.07	0.09	0.15						
Currently schooling (%)				0.06	0.13	0.16	0.06	0.19	0.26
Mother alive (%)				-0.34	-0.15	-0.02			
Tolerate violence (%)				0.14	0.2	0.23	0.12	0.24	0.42
Women beating (%)				-0.29	-0.23	-0.16			
Community violence (%)				0.12	0.25	0.29	0.02	0.2	0.45
HHs government aid (%)				0.07	0.17	0.27			
HHs no education (%)				0.09	0.15	0.18			
Transactional Relationship (%)							1.34	2.21	2.87
No supervision night (%)							-0.4	-0.24	-0.17
Fear of violence (%)							0.35	0.46	0.67
<i>R</i>²		0.569			0.642			0.775	
<i>Adjusted-R</i>²		0.477			0.528			0.689	
<i>AIC</i>_c		485.023			548.261			562.783	

Note : AIC – Akaike information criterion; AIC_c – corrected Akaike information criterion; VIF – variance inflation factor; Min. – minimum; and Max. – maximum.

Tables 2 and 3 present the OLS and GWR model results, respectively. The GWR model demonstrated lower AIC_c and higher *R*²/*adjusted-R*² values for all forms of violence compared to OLS, suggesting a better fit and a larger proportion of variation in the risk of violence than the OLS model. We also observed an inverse relationship between GWR model performance and violence prevalence, with lower local *R*² values in high-prevalence areas, implying the presence of unaccounted factors in these constituencies (Figure 2).

Figure 2 GWR local R^2 values for the forms of violence.

Our findings show that several risk factors significantly influenced area-level variations in VACY in Namibia, including *having a romantic partner*, *witnessing domestic violence*, *witnessing community violence*, and *residing in a single-parent household* for SV; *living in a household receiving government aid* and *residing in a household with a head with no education* for PV; and *transactional relationships* and *fear of violence* for EV (Tables 2 – 3). Shared risk factors included *witnessing parental abuse of siblings* (for all three forms), *being in school*, *beliefs justifying that women should tolerate violence for family unity*, and *witnessing community violence* (PV and EV). Protective factors included *paid/self-employment* (SV), *living biological mother* (though not locally significant, PV), *attitudes justifying the beating of women* (PV), and *lack of parental supervision at night* (EV). The spatial distribution of coefficients showed varying influences across Namibia, with some constituencies showing stronger influences and others showing weaker effects (Figures 3–5). Notably, PV and EV shared more risk factors than SV, suggesting that their spatial aetiologies may be similar. This spatial variability may be further driven by complex interactions between social and physical environments and cultural factors that were not examined in our study (Gentz et al, 2021).

Figure 3 Statistically significant risk factors for SV.

Figure 4 Statistically significant risk factors for PV.

Figure 5 Statistically significant risk factors for EV.

4. Conclusion

This study is the first to explore the geospatial patterns and risk factors of VACYP in Namibia, revealing significant regional disparities. Our findings emphasise the need for geographically targeted interventions, as broad approaches to violence prevention are unlikely to be effective. Key drivers, such as having a romantic partner, exposure to domestic or community violence, school attendance, and supportive attitudes towards violence against women, highlight the need for policies addressing domestic violence, school safety, cultural norms, and other structural factors. The GWR analysis provided valuable insights into spatial variations, underscoring the necessity of disaggregating forms of violence. Geospatial modelling offers critical guidance to policymakers to effectively allocate resources and reduce violence in high-risk areas.

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References

Akmatov, M. K. (2011) Child abuse in 28 developing and transitional countries—results from the Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 40(1), 219-227.

Gentz, S., Zeng, C. & Ruiz-Casares, M. (2021) The role of individual-, family-, and school-level resilience in the subjective well-being of children exposed to violence in Namibia. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 119(Pt 2), 105087.

Hillis, S., Mercy, J., Amobi, A. & Kress, H. (2016) Global Prevalence of Past-year Violence Against Children: A Systematic Review and Minimum Estimates. *Pediatrics*, 137(3), e20154079.

Hillis, S. D., Mercy, J. A. & Saul, J. R. (2017) The enduring impact of violence against children. *Psychol Health Med*, 22(4), 393-405.

MGEPEWS, NSA & I-TECH (2020) *Violence Against Children and Youth in Namibia: Findings from the Violence Against Children and Youth Survey, 2019 (Full Report)*. Windhoek, Namibia.

Shinyemba, T. W., Shiode, S. & Devries, K. (2024) Application of geospatial analysis in health research: A systematic review of methodological aspects of studies on violence against children and young people. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 151, 106730.

Biographies

Tobias Willem Shinyemba is a PhD candidate in Geography at Birkbeck, University of London, with an MSc in Applied Statistics and Demography. His research explores the geospatial patterns and underlying risk factors of violence against children and young people in Namibia.

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Karen Devries is a Professor at the LSHTM and a social epidemiologist specialising in child protection and violence prevention for children, adolescents, and women. Her research integrates quantitative and qualitative methods to explore the causes and consequences of violence, develop interventions, and address ethical and measurement challenges.